

THE INTRODUCTION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

health is one of the most important components of human adulthood, the human right to self-development, which no one can afford, active participation in personal and public life. As you know, in our society, human health, physical perfection, and possession of a healthy lifestyle culture are considered extremely important social values. Ensuring the health of the nation, the preservation of the gene pool fluffy is quite positive only thanks to a healthy lifestyle is solved in a way. These, in turn, are all social institutions of society; family, education and upbringing citizens of our society who have access to residential premises, mahallas and independent education, expressing the content and essence of a lifestyle, forcing young people to be vigilant and knowledgeable, puts the question of educating a harmonious personality at a dead end.

Health is one of the most important components of human adulthood, the right of the individual to self-development, personal and active participation in the life of society is a pledge. Non-communicable in our country, prevention, treatment and control of diseases and their risk factors, consistent measures are being taken to reduce premature mortality and morbidity of the population.

The way of life of people formed in the process of historical development of movement and activity. Towards the process of accurate historical progress custom-based practices are repeated over time. They, in turn, need habits of action, which have become habits, reveal the nature of life. A healthy lifestyle includes strengthening a person's life aspirations, health and a set of his actions aimed at preventing violations of the law. So, a healthy lifestyle is what makes people take care of their health activities aimed at preservation and improvement.

Despite the health care reforms, medical workers and one of the main tasks of teachers is to maintain a healthy lifestyle. malaise was considered the prevention of a disease caused by malaise.

The purpose of the study: education of healthy lifestyle skills for students at the stages of formation and professional training in a higher educational institution, studying the skills of

healthy behavior of young people, as well as the system of representations.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS Studying the lifestyle of medical students and their healthy lifestyle, a questionnaire was developed to determine their understanding of the style. The questionnaire consists of 25 open questions. Before the questionnaire was conducted, students were instructed, 400 volunteers took part in the survey Undergraduate and graduate students of the Tashkent Medical Academy, in particular medical, medical and pedagogical faculties, 1st year undergraduates of all directions were present. Of these, 41.5% (166) of girls (women) and 58.5% (234) of boys (men) I got a job.

A healthy lifestyle is closely linked to proper nutrition. According to the World Health Organization, physical activity and non-compliance with dietary norms and rules, salt, sugar, fat content, excessive consumption of foods and sweets, of which there are many, as well as rationally in youth due to insufficient intake of vitamins and minerals, lag in growth and mental development, and in adults-cardiovascular, endocrine, a number of diseases that lead to premature death of a person, such as a malignant tumor. Do you follow the rules of proper nutrition?

While only 23% of students answered "yes" to the question "why?", 60% answered "Yes" sometimes, 17% of students, however, answered "no".

Health care and physical culture and sports in the republic, in the normative legal acts adopted in order to reform these systems, the importance of forming a healthy lifestyle among the population is directed as one of the most important directions of state policy in this area. In particular, until 2025, the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the development of physical culture and sports, until 2022, the concept of disease prevention, maintaining a healthy lifestyle and increasing the level of physical activity of the population, as well as a healthy lifestyle measures for the widespread introduction of a lifestyle and the further development of mass sports were approved and aimed at implementation.

You regularly visit various sports clubs, gyms, and swimming pools. to be present? 14% of students answered the question - "I visit regularly", 27% - "I can't because I have the desire, I don't have enough money," 44% - I can't because I don't have the time and desire, 15% insisted that they couldn't answer.

When asked about your personal attitude to a healthy lifestyle, 77.5% will answer that this person is important for health, and I try to stick to it, 6.5% even without him you can live, 16% replied that sometimes it is necessary to observe it.

In addition, the formation of a healthy lifestyle among students gathered their personal opinions on what to do. The majority of students (60.0%) believe that the role of the family in shaping a healthy lifestyle is of great importance 30% of students are interested in financing a family for a healthy lifestyle 20% of respondents replied that for a healthy lifestyle, students should have sufficient conditions in educational institutions and dormitories, they insisted that this was the case.

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